

Instructional Competence and Supervisory Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in Relation to Teachers Performance

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Abstract:

School Heads perform multiple role expectations. As instructional leaders, they are expected to develop the quality of instructions; and as administrators, they too are expected to exercise proper supervisory skills. Stressful as it may seem, School Heads are key figures that can impact the performance of teachers and learners alike (Manasse, 2015). This study aimed to determine the level of instructional competence and the supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads in relation to teachers' performance in Tayasan II District, Division of Negros Oriental for the School Year 2019-2020. The study variables included age, sex, length of service and highest educational attainment. The study concentrated School Head's instructional competence and supervisory skills. The study investigated on School Heads' instructional delivery, classroom management and formative assessments, also on their financial management, conflict management and teachers' professional development. The result of the study showed that School Head's Instructional Competence and Supervisory Skills were all on high level. There was no significant difference in the level of instructional competence of public elementary School Heads when they are grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables. There was a significant difference in the level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads when they are grouped and compared according sex and highest educational attainment. The study revealed that there was no significant difference in the level of Teachers performance and there was no significant relationship between the level of instructional competence of public elementary School Heads and the level of teachers' performance.

Keywords: Competence, Supervisory Skills, School Heads, Teachers Performance

Introduction:

Background of the Study

School Heads perform multiple role expectations. As instructional leaders, they are expected to develop the quality of instructions; and as administrators, they too are expected to exercise proper supervisory skills. Stressful as it may seem, School Heads are key figures that can impact the performance of teachers and learners alike. It is therefore needed that School Heads must possess an inner compass to provide their schools with a steadfast leadership using their supervisory and instructional skills (Manasse, 2015).

School Head's instructional and supervisory skills are the driving force that often leads to better teachers' performance. When teachers are empowered and fully supported by their school heads, it will have a ripple effect on students' academic performance (Goden, et al., 2016).

One major emphasis in the educational arena in the early 21st century has been the continuing demand for greater accountability to increase teachers' performance. Academic expectations require schools to ensure that students achieve mastery of curriculum objectives, and local schools focus on implementing those requirements to the best of their ability by improving first teachers' competence and performance. As a result, leading instructional efforts in a school has evolved into a primary role for school principals (Stronge, et al., 2019).

Instructional competence and supervisory skills include various roles and responsibilities that entail technical, professional and interpersonal aspects. Leaders who can provide the necessary leadership when managing the teachers' performance can have a large impact on their school's work environment and if the impact is positive, it may lead to teachers practicing and displaying desired behaviors in the workplace, especially in their commitment towards the school organizations.

As a Public School District Supervisor, the researcher is constantly working with various School Heads in his district. It is his observation that said School Heads perform their duties and responsibilities well but are unable to translate their efforts in to good results because teachers are not able to hit the target results in their respective classes. The researcher strongly believes that effective school leaders produce effective teachers, hence, produce good students.

These observations and personal encounters motivated the researcher in conducting this study. The researcher hopes that the findings of this study, he will be able to identify the challenges will help him propose an action plan whose inputs will benefit the school heads, the teachers and indirectly, the pupils.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of instructional competence and the supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads in relation to teachers' performance of Tayasan II District, Division of Negros Oriental for the School Year 2019-2020.

Literature Review:

In a 2016 study conducted by Manaseh (2016) of the University of College Education in Tanzania, two objectives guided their study: to explore the informants' understanding on the concept of instructional leadership; and to examine the role played by heads of schools in managing the instructional program to enhance teachers' classroom instruction and students' learning. It draws on the qualitative data generated from interviews, focus group discussions, and observations. The informants for that study were senior academic masters/mistresses, teachers and students. The study findings confirm that Head of Schools, Senior Academic Masters, teachers and students were not familiar with the concept of instructional leadership. On the other hand, the instructional program was not effectively managed as heads of departments were not involved in curriculum coordination, syllabi were not covered on time and the head of schools did not undertake classroom observations or engage in review of curriculum materials. The paper, however, concluded that without an effective management of the instructional program in favor of promoting teachers' classroom instruction and students' learning, efforts to that effect are doomed to fail. (Manaseh, 2016).

School Heads are usually charged with the responsibility for teacher development. One of the reasons often given for the failure to carry out this task effectively is a lack of time. Classroom visitation, usually considered to be a key component of teacher development, can be very time consuming, as can conferences. The problem, then, becomes one of how to use the school heads limited time most effectively. Is the commonly accepted class visitation/post conference method the most productive, or could greater results be obtained by devoting all, or at least most, of that time to teacher-principal conferences designed to help the teacher discover his/her own strengths and weaknesses (Westerberg, 2013).

It's a daunting but all-too-common sight for many teachers: A classroom full of rowdy students who are unable to focus on the lesson. Classroom management techniques may get things back on track, but valuable time has already been lost. Many experienced teachers know that making meaningful connections with students is one of the most effective ways to prevent disruptions in the first place, and a new study set out to assess this approach. In classrooms where teachers used a series of techniques centered around establishing, maintaining, and restoring relationships, academic engagement increased by 33 percent and disruptive behavior decreased by 75 percent—making the time students spent in the classroom more worthwhile and productive (Terada, 2019).

Methodology:

This section describes the research design employed in the research undertaking, the subject and the respondents of the study, research instrument, its validity and reliability, data gathering procedure, the analytical schemes as well as the statistical tools that were used for the analysis and interpretation of data.

Research Design

This study employed descriptive research design to determine the level of instructional competence and the supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads in relation to teachers' performance.

A descriptive research is valuable in providing facts in which scientific judgment maybe based on assessing the present study. Furthermore, a descriptive design is appropriate for studies which aims to find out what prevails in the present conditions or relationships, held opinions and beliefs, processes and effects, and developing trends. This research design is a scientific method which involves observing and describing the behavior of a subject without influencing it in any way (Bueno, 2016).

This research design is considered appropriate for this particular study because its purpose was to find out the level of School Heads' Instructional Competence and Supervisory Skills in relation to Teachers' Performance. It is the nature of this study to assess the condition of things in their present state. Likewise, it delves into the relationship among variables that are considered in the study as well as the influence of one variable to another.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the 159 public elementary school teachers who are officially employed and assigned in the Tayasan II District, since the total number of respondents is manageable total enumeration was employed.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents according to their school.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

School	Population (N)	Percentage (%)
A	9	5.7
B	9	5.7
C	5	3.1
D	10	6.3
E	9	5.7
F	11	6.9
G	5	3.1
H	7	4.4
I	9	5.7
J	10	6.3
K	11	6.9
L	7	4.4
M	7	4.4
N	7	4.4
O	11	6.9
P	32	20.1
Total	159	100.0

Data Gathering Instruments

This study used a self-made questionnaire in gathering all the data, mainly from teacher-respondents. It was divided in 2 parts. Part I contained queries on respondents' profile such as age, sex, highest educational attainment and length of service, Part II was the questionnaire proper consisting of 30 items on instructional competence and 30 items on supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads, 10 items per area.

The respondents were given options for their answer. The assessment of the level of instructional competence and the supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads in each item under the aforementioned areas were measured from the continuum of 5 to 1 with 5 interpreted as "very high level", 4 as "high level", 3 as "moderate level", 2 as "low level" and 1 as "very low level". Further, the description below will be used in the assessment of each question:

Scores	Description
5	Always
4	Often
3	Sometimes
2	Rarely
1	Almost never

Validity

According to Cook (2015), Validity refers to the degree to which evidence and theory support the interpretation of test score entailed by the proposed uses of tests. In other words, validity describes how well one can legitimately trust the results of a test as interpreted for a specific purpose.

The survey questionnaire was presented to Five (5) jurors who are experts in the fields of Education and Research for further evaluation, comments and suggestions. Each of them was requested to determine if each segment are suitable questions to gather related data, supporting the area of the studies.

The first, second and third jurors are Doctor in Developmental Education, currently the District Supervisors, in the Division of Negros Oriental, the fourth and fifth jurors are Doctor of Education and currently the District Supervisors, in the Division of Negros Oriental.

To determine the validity of the research instrument, the researcher adapted the criteria developed for the evaluation of survey questionnaires set forth by Carter B. Good and Douglas E. Scates. The interpretations were as follows: Excellent (4.04 – 5.00); Very Good (3.28 - 4.03); Good (2.52 – 3.27); Poor (2.51 – 1.76); Very Poor (1.00 – 1.75). The average rating of the five jurors is 4.53, interpreted as "excellent" which means that the survey instrument is valid.

Reliability

Reliability estimates evaluate the stability of measures, internal consistency of measurement instruments, and inter-rater reliability of instrument scores. Validity is the extent to which the interpretations of the results of a test are warranted, which depends on the particular use the test is intended to serve (McGregor, 2016).

Since the research instrument is a self-made, the reliability will be established. To establish the reliability of the research instrument, the Cronbach Alpha will be used. The Cronbach Alpha is used whenever the researcher has items that are not scored simply as right or wrong (Santos, 2016). Cronbach Alpha is a measure of internal consistency, that is, how closely related a set of items are as a group. It is considered to be a measure of scale reliability. A "high" value for alpha does not imply that the measure is unidimensional.

To determine the reliability of the questionnaire, the researcher administered the instrument to 30 public elementary school teachers of Tayasan I District in the Division of Negros Oriental, 10 teachers from Matuog Central School; 7 teachers from Tamao Elementary School; 7 teachers from Linao Elementary School and 6 teachers from Ilaya Elementary School. The reliability index for Instructional Competence was 0.860 and for Supervisory Skills was 0.996 and when taken as a whole was 0.939, which means that the questionnaires was within a high level of reliability, interpreted as "highly reliable".

Data Gathering Procedures

For the smoother conduct of the study the researcher employed the following procedures. There was a letter of request addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent for the conduct of the study within the Tayasan II District was submitted for approval. Upon approval, a letter request was distributed to the school heads of all component schools. After securing the approval for the second request, questionnaires were administered to target respondents.

The data gathered from the responses of the respondents were tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The raw data were transformed into numerical code guided by a coding manual. This allowed computer processing, statistical derivations and tabular presentation. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used in the computer processing of the encoded data.

Statistical Tools

In the analysis of the data, various statistical tools were employed depending on the objectives of the study.

Objective No. 1, used the frequency count and percentage to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, length of service and highest educational attainment.

This statistical tool is appropriate to be used in establishing the typical characteristics of the group respondents of the study. A percentage frequency distribution is a display of data that specifies the percentage of observations that exist for each data point or grouping of data points. It is a particularly useful method of expressing the relative frequency of survey responses and other data (Lesvin, 2016).

Objective No. 2, used the Mean to determine the level of instructional competence of public elementary School Heads in the areas of instructional delivery, classroom observation and formative assessment.

The statistical mean has a wide range of applicability in various types of experimentation. This type of calculation eliminates random errors and helps to derive a more accurate result than a result derived from a single experiment. The statistical mean can also be used to interpret statistical data. Some important properties make statistical mean very useful for measuring central tendency (Radisson, 2016).

The mean scores were interpreted as follows:

Range Score	Description	Verbal Interpretation
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4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very High Level
3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	High Level
2.50 - 3.49	Sometimes	Moderate Level
1.50 - 2.49	Rarely	Low Level
1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Level

Objective No. 3, used the Mean to determine the level of instructional competence of public elementary School Heads in the areas of instructional delivery, classroom observation and formative assessment when they are grouped according to age, sex, length of service and highest educational attainment.

Objective No. 4, used the Mean to determine the level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads in the areas of financial management, conflict resolution and teachers' professional development.

The mean scores were interpreted as follows:

Range Score	Description	Verbal Interpretation
4.50 - 5.00	Always	Very High Level
3.50 - 4.49	Oftentimes	High Level
2.50 - 3.49	Sometimes	Moderate Level
1.50 - 2.49	Rarely	Low Level
1.00 - 1.49	Almost never	Very Low Level

Objective No. 5, used the Mean to determine the level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads in the areas of financial management, conflict resolution and teachers' professional development when they are grouped according to age, sex, length of service and highest educational attainment.

Objective No. 6, used the Mean to determine the level of teachers' performance.

The level of teachers performance were measured based on DepEd IPCRF rating as follows:

Range Score	Verbal Interpretation
4.50-5.00	Outstanding
3.50-4.49	Very Satisfactory
2.50-4.49	Satisfactory
1.50-2.49	Unsatisfactory
Below 1.49	Poor

Objective No. 7, used the Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant difference in the level of instructional competence of public elementary School Heads when they are grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables.

Mann-Whitney U test is the non-parametric alternative test to the independent sample t-test. It is a non-parametric test that is used to compare two sample means that come from the same population, and used to test whether two sample means are equal or not. Usually, the Mann-Whitney U test is used when the data is ordinal or when the assumptions of the t-test are not met (Collins, 2017).

If the p value is large, the data do not give you any reason to reject the null hypothesis. This is not the same as saying that the two populations are the same. You just have no compelling evidence that they differ. If you have small samples, the Mann-Whitney test has little power. In fact, if the total sample size is seven or less, the Mann-Whitney test will always give a p value greater than 0.05 no matter how much the groups differ.

Objective No. 8, used the Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant difference in the level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads when they are grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 9, used the Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant difference in the level of teachers' performance when they are grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 10, used the Spearman's rho to determine the significant relationship between the level of instructional competence of public elementary School Heads and the level of teachers' performance.

Objective No. 11, used the Spearman's rho to determine the significant relationship between the level supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads and the level of teachers' performance.

A Spearman correlation coefficient is also referred to as Spearman rank correlation or Spearman's rho. It is typically denoted either with the Greek letter rho (ρ), or r_s . Like all correlation coefficients, Spearman's rho measures the strength of association between two variables. As such, the Spearman correlation coefficient is similar to the Pearson correlation coefficient.

Finally, the computation of the p -value were interpreted using the following guide.

- a. Reject the null hypothesis if the p -value is equal to or less than 0.05 level of significance.
- b. Accept the null hypothesis if the p -value is greater than 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age, Sex, Length of Service and Highest Educational Attainment

Table 2

Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Variables used in this Study

Variable Grouping	Classification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	Younger (Below 37 years old)	77	48.40
	Older (37 years old and above)	82	51.60
Sex	Male	25	15.70
	Female	134	84.30
Length of Service	Shorter (Below 10 years)	73	45.90
	Longer (10 years and above)	86	54.10
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower (College Degree)	109	68.60
	Higher (Master's degree and PhD)	50	31.40
Total		159	100.00

Table 2 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, length of service and highest educational attainment. In terms of Age, 77 or 48.40% were younger (below 37 years old) respondents and 82 or 51.60% were older (37 years old and above) respondents. In terms of Sex, 25 or 15.70% were male respondents and 134 or 84.30% were female respondents. In terms of Length of Service, 73 or 45.9% belonged to shorter tenure (below 10 years) respondents and 86 or 54.10% belonged to longer tenure (10 years and above) respondents. In terms of Highest Educational Attainment, 109 or 68.60% belonged to lower (college degree) respondents and 50 or 31.40% belonged to higher (Master's degree and PhD) respondents. The result of the study showed that majority of the respondents belong to the older age bracket. Most of them were female and most of them were tenured. Majority of the respondents have no post graduate studies. According to Sarker (2015), earlier studies suggest age is positively associated with job performance while others use length of service, or tenure, as a predictor of job-related skills.

Level of Instructional Competence of Public Elementary School Heads in terms of Instructional Delivery, Classroom Observation, and Formative Assessment

Table 3
Level of Instructional Competence of Public Elementary School Heads in terms of Instructional Delivery

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1 ensures that instructional delivery is at par with curricular requirements.	4.53	Very High Level
2 ensures that instructional materials are updated and DepEd compliant.	4.49	High Level
3 encourages teacher to improve utilization of ICT-based learning.	4.45	High Level
4 provides plan on how to achieve academic goals.	4.47	High Level
5 sets target on what to achieve academic excellence as top priority.	4.36	High Level
6 reminds teachers to reach and deliver academic targets.	4.53	Very High Level
7 asks everyone to share best academic practices.	4.48	High Level
8 takes time to randomly check instructional materials of teachers.	4.43	High Level
9 sets proper academic expectations with teachers and students.	4.33	High Level
10 spearheads the achievement of school's mission & vision.	4.33	High Level
Overall Mean	4.44	High Level

Table 3 shows the level of instructional competence of public elementary school heads in terms of instructional delivery.

Item Nos. 1 and 6 which state, "ensures that instructional delivery is at par with curricular requirements" and "reminds teachers to reach and deliver academic targets" got the highest mean score of 4.53, interpreted as "very high level". Meanwhile, Item Nos. 9 and 10 which state, "sets proper academic expectations with teachers and students" and "spearheads the achievement of school's mission & vision" got the lowest mean score of 4.33, interpreted as "high level". The overall mean score was 4.44, interpreted as "high level".

The results of the study implied that some School Heads are not setting proper expectations with teachers and students as to academic plans, future trainings needed, projects, among others. Equally, some of the respondents indicated that there is a need for some School Heads to improve on taking the lead role towards achieving scholastic goals for their own academic organization.

In a 2016 study conducted by Manaseh (2016) of the University of College Education in Tanzania, the study findings confirm that Head of Schools, Senior Academic Masters, teachers and students were not familiar with the concept of instructional leadership. On the other hand, the instructional program was not effectively managed as heads of departments were not involved in curriculum coordination, syllabi were not covered on time and the head of schools did not undertake classroom observations or engage in review of curriculum materials. The paper, however, concluded that without an effective management of the instructional program in favor of promoting teachers' classroom instruction and students' learning, efforts to that effect are doomed to fail. (Manaseh, 2016).

Table 4

Level of Instructional Competence of Public Elementary School Heads in terms of Classroom Observation

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1 consistent & on-time during classroom observation.	4.54	Very High Level
2 ensuring that that the objectives of C.O. are accomplished.	4.54	Very High Level
3 aiming to improve instructional/teaching skills.	4.48	High Level
4 giving proper feedback to teachers.	4.60	Very High Level
5 helping teachers achieve school's mission & vision through effective teaching.	4.58	Very High Level
6 ensuring that C.O. is being done to achieve higher teaching-learning experience.	4.52	Very High Level
7 making sure that areas for improvement are being discussed thoroughly with individual teachers after classroom observation.	4.40	High Level
8 very open in giving compliments to teachers or say thank you for good performance.	4.43	High Level
9 providing coaching sessions in a friendly and cordial manner.	4.50	Very High Level
10 treating teachers as co-workers, not just as subordinates.	4.53	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.51	Very High Level

Table 4 shows the level of instructional competence of public elementary school heads in terms of classroom observation.

Item No. 4 which states, "Giving proper feedback to teachers" got the highest mean score of 4.60, interpreted as "very high level". Meanwhile, Item No. 7 which states, "Improvement are being discussed thoroughly with individual teachers after classroom observation" got the lowest mean score of 4.40, interpreted as "high level". The overall mean score was 4.51, interpreted as "very high level".

The result indicated that there are times when the documented outcome of the classroom observation is not used as basis in discussing improvement plans with teachers. It is very important to note that the discussion on how and what to improve in the classroom must always be based on documented results from actual observation to avoid missing key and important points. By using documented observations, real issues can be fully discussed. This is also needed to be fair with teachers.

School Heads are usually charged with the responsibility for teacher development. One of the reasons often given for the failure to carry out this task effectively is a lack of time. Classroom visitation, usually considered to be a key component of teacher development, can be very time consuming, as can conferences. The problem, then, becomes one of how to use the school heads limited time most effectively. Is the commonly accepted class visitation/post conference method the most productive, or could greater results be obtained by devoting all, or at least most, of that time to teacher-principal conferences designed to help the teacher discover his/her own strengths and weaknesses (Westerberg, 2013).

Table 5

Level of Instructional Competence of Public Elementary School Heads in terms of Formative Assessment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1 instructs teachers to have proper filing of test sheets.	4.33	High Level
2 ensures that low assessment areas are properly identified and given proper attention by teachers.	4.30	High Level
3 ensures that assessments reflect the true content of lectures.	4.41	High Level
4 checks lesson plans or modified DLLs shows index of mastery.	4.34	High Level
5 aims in developing higher order thinking skills.	4.37	High Level
6 reminds teachers that assessments must be reflective of school-taught values.	4.43	High Level
7 ensures that assessments are strategized in consonance with curriculum requirements.	4.45	High Level
8 checks that assessments are learner-centered, reflective of lesson contents.	4.40	High Level

9	ensures that assessments are learner-centered and reflective of class discussions/lesson contents.	4.40	High Level
10	requires parent's signature on their test sheets	4.37	High Level
Overall Mean		4.38	High Level

Table 5 shows the level of instructional competence of public elementary school heads in terms of formative assessment.

Item No. 7 which states, "ensures that assessments are strategized in consonance with curriculum requirements" got the highest mean score of 4.40, interpreted as "high level". Meanwhile, Item No. 2 which states, "properly identified and given proper attention by teachers" got the lowest mean score of 4.30, interpreted as "high level". The overall mean score was 4.38, interpreted as "high level".

The results indicated the need for a more focused administration of formative assessment materials. One must remember that the main purpose of having formative assessment is to directly identify the needs of learners, assisting them towards value-formation with the specific need to improve their own academic needs based on the results of the assessments.

Garrison and Ehringhaus (2019), said that one of the key components of engaging students in the assessment of their own learning is providing them with descriptive feedback as they learn. In fact, research shows descriptive feedback to be the most significant instructional strategy to move students forward in their learning. Descriptive feedback provides students with an understanding of what they are doing well, links to classroom learning, and gives specific input on how to reach the next step in the learning progression. In other words, descriptive feedback is not a grade, a sticker, or "good job!" A significant body of research indicates that such limited feedback does not lead to improved student learning.

Level of Instructional Competence of Public Elementary School Heads in terms of Instructional Delivery, Classroom Observation, and Formative Assessment and When They are Grouped According to Age, Sex, Length of Service and Highest Educational Attainment

Table 6
Level of Instructional Competence of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Instructional Delivery and when Grouped According to Age

Items	Age Younger		Older		
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
1	4.48	High Level	4.57	Very High Level	
2	4.47	High Level	4.51	Very High Level	
3	4.43	High Level	4.48	High Level	
4	4.43	High Level	4.51	Very High Level	
5	4.29	High Level	4.44	High Level	
6	4.48	High Level	4.59	Very High Level	
7	4.45	High Level	4.50	Very High Level	
8	4.39	High Level	4.46	High Level	
9	4.30	High Level	4.37	High Level	
10	4.30	High Level	4.37	High Level	
Overall Mean		4.40	High Level	4.48	High Level

Table 6 shows the level of instructional competence of public elementary school heads in the area instructional delivery and when grouped according to age.

Item Nos. 1 and 6 which state, "ensures that instructional delivery is at par with curricular requirements" and "reminds teachers to reach and deliver academic targets" got the highest mean score of 4.48 for younger group, interpreted as "high level", while Item No. 6 which states, "reminds teachers to reach and deliver academic targets" also got the highest mean score of 4.59 for older group, interpreted as "very high level". Meanwhile, Item No. 5 which states, "sets target on what to achieve academic excellence as top priority" got the lowest mean score of 4.29 for younger group, interpreted as "high level", while Item Nos. 9 and 10 which state, "sets proper academic expectations with teachers and students" and "spearheads the achievement of school's mission & vision" got the lowest mean score of 4.37 for older group, interpreted as "high level". The overall mean scores were 4.40 for younger and 4.48 for older group, both were interpreted as "high level".

The result of the study indicated that across age groups, the setting of academic priorities and the setting of expectations with teachers and students are less attended to by School Heads. This means that there are School

Heads who are less taking-on their job as instructional heads of each school. This part of being instructional managers is really important for School Heads to fulfill because this will help ensure that teachers and students are guided on where they are heading to. The ability to provide a heads-up and set proper expectations will guide everyone.

Historically, principals have been characterized as change agents who work with a limited and constantly evolving sphere of influence — they are at once leaders, administrators and middle managers who mediate tensions between policy-as-designed and policies-as-implemented. Principals face challenges of increasing complexity and frequency as they fulfill their functions and provide direction and support while seeking to influence conditions related to teaching and learning in times where uncertainty is the norm and reform is often implemented from unstable footing. External environmental pressures constrain leader influence and direction and can conflict with the established norms, values and beliefs of the internal social systems of organizations. Principals operate precariously in between these internal and external worlds, and the relative lack of success of school reform efforts is evidence of the breadth and depth of the challenge they face on a daily basis (Hidalgo, 2016).

Table 7
Level of Instructional Competence of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Instructional Delivery and when grouped According to Sex

Items	Sex Male		Sex Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1 ensures that instructional delivery is at par with curricular requirements.	4.40	High Level	4.55	Very High Level
2 ensures that instructional materials are updated and DepEd compliant.	4.40	High Level	4.51	Very High Level
3 encourages teacher to improve utilization of ICT-based learning.	4.48	High Level	4.45	High Level
4 provides plan on how to achieve academic goals.	4.40	High Level	4.49	High Level
5 sets target on what to achieve academic excellence as top priority.	4.20	High Level	4.40	High Level
6 reminds teachers to reach and deliver academic targets.	4.48	High Level	4.54	Very High Level
7 asks everyone to share best academic practices.	4.40	High Level	4.49	High Level
8 takes time to randomly check instructional materials of teachers.	4.36	High Level	4.44	High Level
9 sets proper academic expectations with teachers and students.	4.28	High Level	4.34	High Level
10 spearheads the achievement of school's mission & vision.	4.28	High Level	4.34	High Level
Overall Mean	4.37	High Level	4.46	High Level

Table 7 shows the level of instructional competence of public elementary school heads in the area instructional delivery and when grouped according to sex.

Item Nos. 1 and 6 which state, "ensures that instructional delivery is at par with curricular requirements" and "reminds teachers to reach and deliver academic targets" got the highest mean score of 4.48 for male group, interpreted as "high level", while Item No. 6 which states, "reminds teachers to reach and deliver academic targets" also got the highest mean score of 4.54 for female group, interpreted as "very high level". Meanwhile, Item No. 5 which states, "sets target on what to achieve academic excellence as top priority" got the lowest mean score of 4.20 for male group, interpreted as "high level", while Item Nos. 9 and 10 which state, "sets proper academic expectations with teachers and students" and "spearheads the achievement of school's mission & vision" got the lowest mean score of 4.34 for female group, interpreted as "high level". The overall mean scores were 4.37 for male and 4.46 for female group, both were interpreted as "high level".

This implies that across sex groups, the concern is about setting of targets. As to Male respondents, setting of academic goals is important and they believed that this must be given proper importance by School Heads. For the Female group, setting of proper expectations with teachers and students is very important, just as much important as seeing the School Heads spearheading the effort to achieve academic goals contained in the school's mission and vision. These skills are very important because these are indicators of School Head's ability to look ahead and anticipate things. With the ability to anticipate comes the ability to provide a work plan to ensure that academic goals are properly worked-on.

According to the research study of the University of Tasmania in 2013, one of the most consistent findings from studies of effective school leadership is that authority to lead need not be located in the person of the leader but can be dispersed within the school between and among people. There is a growing understanding that leadership is embedded in various organizational contexts within school communities, not centrally vested in a

person or an office. The real challenge facing most schools is no longer how to improve but, more importantly, how to sustain improvement. Sustainability will depend upon the school's internal capacity to maintain and support developmental work and sustaining improvement requires the leadership capability of the many rather than the few (universityoftasmania, 2013).

Table 8
Level of Instructional Competence of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Instructional Delivery and when Grouped According to Length of Service

Items	Length of Service			
	Shorter Mean	Interpretation	Longer Mean	Interpretation
1 ensures that instructional delivery is at par with curricular requirements.	4.45	High Level	4.59	Very High Level
2 ensures that instructional materials are updated and DepEd compliant.	4.45	High Level	4.52	Very High Level
3 encourages teacher to improve utilization of ICT-based learning.	4.42	High Level	4.48	High Level
4 provides plan on how to achieve academic goals.	4.40	High Level	4.53	Very High Level
5 sets target on what to achieve academic excellence as top priority.	4.27	High Level	4.44	High Level
6 reminds teachers to reach and deliver academic targets.	4.47	High Level	4.59	Very High Level
7 asks everyone to share best academic practices.	4.48	High Level	4.48	High Level
8 takes time to randomly check instructional materials of teachers.	4.41	High Level	4.44	High Level
9 sets proper academic expectations with teachers and students.	4.29	High Level	4.37	High Level
10 spearheads the achievement of school's mission & vision.	4.29	High Level	4.37	High Level
Overall Mean	4.39	High Level	4.48	High Level

Table 8 shows the level of instructional competence of public elementary school heads in the area instructional delivery and when grouped according to length of service.

Item No. 7 which states, "asks everyone to share best academic practices" got the highest mean score of 4.48 for shorter group, interpreted as "high level", while Item Nos. 1 and 6 which state, "ensures that instructional delivery is at par with curricular requirements" and "reminds teachers to reach and deliver academic targets" also got the highest mean score of 4.59 for longer group, interpreted as "very high level". Meanwhile, Item No. 5 which states, "sets target on what to achieve academic excellence as top priority" got the lowest mean score of 4.27 for shorter group, interpreted as "high level", while Item Nos. 9 and 10 which state, "sets proper academic expectations with teachers and students" and "spearheads the achievement of school's mission & vision" got the lowest mean score of 4.37 for longer group, interpreted as "high level". The overall mean scores were 4.39 for shorter and 4.48 for longer group, both were interpreted as "high level".

The result of the study indicated that regardless of their tenure, the respondents indicated that the common need among School Heads to be improved is their ability to look forward ahead of the situations, make credible academic predictions and improve their visible ability to lead. According to the shorter tenured respondents, it is important for School Heads to set forth academic targets to achieve excellence while for the more tenured respondents, they wanted to see more from their School Head's a higher sense of responsibility to achieve excellence within the context of the school's mission and vision. At all angle, the ability to make projections on how to achieve academic excellence and planning on how to work-on and achieve such targets is truly critical and important because it is only in having such plans that the targets may be achieved.

A broad and longstanding consensus in leadership theory holds that leaders in all walks of life and all kinds of organizations, public and private, need to depend on others to accomplish the group's purpose and need to encourage the development of leadership across the organization. Schools are no different. Principals who get high marks from teachers for creating a strong climate for instruction in their schools also receive higher marks than other principals for spurring leadership in the faculty, according to the research from the universities of Minnesota and Toronto (Wallace, 2016).

Table 9
Level of Instructional Competence of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Instructional Delivery and when Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Highest Educational Attainment			
	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation

1	ensures that instructional delivery is at par with curricular requirements.	4.53	Very High Level	4.52	Very High Level
2	ensures that instructional materials are updated and DepEd compliant.	4.48	High Level	4.52	Very High Level
3	encourages teacher to improve utilization of ICT-based learning.	4.42	High Level	4.52	Very High Level
4	provides plan on how to achieve academic goals.	4.48	High Level	4.46	High Level
5	sets target on what to achieve academic excellence as top priority.	4.38	High Level	4.34	High Level
6	reminds teachers to reach and deliver academic targets.	4.53	Very High Level	4.54	Very High Level
7	asks everyone to share best academic practices.	4.48	High Level	4.48	High Level
8	takes time to randomly check instructional materials of teachers.	4.43	High Level	4.42	High Level
9	sets proper academic expectations with teachers and students.	4.35	High Level	4.30	High Level
10	spearheads the achievement of school's mission & vision.	4.35	High Level	4.30	High Level
Overall Mean		4.44	High Level	4.44	High Level

Table 9 shows the level of instructional competence of public elementary school heads in the area instructional delivery and when grouped according to highest educational attainment.

Item Nos. 1 and 6 which state, "ensures that instructional delivery is at par with curricular requirements" and "reminds teachers to reach and deliver academic targets" also got the highest mean score of 4.53 for lower group, interpreted as "very high level", while Item No. 6 which states, "reminds teachers to reach and deliver academic targets" got the highest mean score of 4.54 for higher group, interpreted as "very high level. Meanwhile, Item Nos. 9 and 10 which state, "sets proper academic expectations with teachers and students" and "spearheads the achievement of school's mission & vision" got the lowest mean score of 4.35 for lower group and 4.30 for higher group, interpreted as "high level". The overall mean scores were 4.44 for both lower and higher group, interpreted as "high level".

The result of the study indicated that regardless of the respondents' highest educational attainment, the respondents clearly and consistently indicated the need for school heads to step up in delivering the mandate of its office, and that is to lead. The lowest mean scores showed that the teachers indeed want to consistently see their School Heads to be able to set expectations to teachers and students as to what direction does he want to lead the school in as far as achieving academic excellence is concerned. Strongly, the results also showed that the respondents wanted their School Heads to be visible instructional leaders in their own respective academic communities.

Leaders who can provide the necessary leadership when managing the teachers' performance can have a large impact on their school's work environment and if the impact is positive, it may lead to teachers practicing and displaying desired behaviors in the workplace, especially in their commitment towards the school organizations (Goden, et al., 2016).

Table 10
Level of Instructional Competence of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Classroom Observation and when Grouped According to Age

Items		Age Younger		Older	
		Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1	consistent & on-time during classroom observation.	4.48	High Level	4.60	Very High Level
2	ensuring that that the objectives of C.O. are accomplished.	4.51	Very High Level	4.57	Very High Level
3	aiming to improve instructional/teaching skills.	4.47	High Level	4.49	High Level
4	giving proper feedback to teachers.	4.60	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
5	helping teachers achieve school's mission & vision through effective teaching.	4.55	Very High Level	4.61	Very High Level
6	ensuring that C.O. is being done to achieve higher teaching-learning experience.	4.47	High Level	4.57	Very High Level
7	making sure that areas for improvement are being discussed thoroughly with individual teachers after classroom observation.	4.31	High Level	4.48	High Level
8	very open in giving compliments to teachers or say thank you for good performance.	4.39	High Level	4.48	High Level
9	providing coaching sessions in a friendly and cordial manner.	4.47	High Level	4.52	Very High Level

10	treating teachers as co-workers, not just as subordinates.	4.48	High Level	4.57	Very High Level
Overall Mean		4.47	High Level	4.55	Very High Level

Table 10 shows the level of instructional competence of public elementary school heads in the area classroom observation and when grouped according to age.

Item No. 4 which states, "giving proper feedback to teachers" got the highest mean score of 4.60 for younger group, interpreted as "very high level", while Item Nos. 4 and 5 which state, "giving proper feedback to teachers" and "helping teachers achieve school's mission & vision through effective teaching" got the highest mean score of 4.61 for older group, interpreted as "very high level". Meanwhile, Item No. 7 which states, "making sure that areas for improvement are being discussed thoroughly with individual teachers after classroom observation" got the lowest mean score of 4.31 for younger group, interpreted as "high level", while Item Nos. 7 and 8 which state, "making sure that areas for improvement are being discussed thoroughly with individual teachers after classroom observation" and "very open in giving compliments to teachers or say thank you for good performance" got the lowest mean score of 4.48 for older group, interpreted as "high level". The overall mean scores were 4.47 for younger, interpreted as "high level" and 4.55 for older group, interpreted as "very high level".

This implies that both the younger and older respondents share the same concern over the sheer inability of some School Heads to take note of the results of the Classroom Observation conducted and use the same as basis in discussing future improvement plans with concerned teachers. This is alarming because it is very difficult to calculate the discussion without basing the very core of it from the results of the actual observations conducted. Whatever documentations obtained during the conduct of the classroom observations, it must be used to maintain neutrality and objectiveness and to ensure that the discussion is fair for the concerned teacher.

According to Helaine (2017), Classroom Observation is a method of evaluating and recording specific information about what is going on within a classroom. Administrators often implement observation periods in order to improve classroom models and learn from other educators. Observing another teacher's classroom and having your own class observed both have several educational purposes, including giving you the ability to describe instructional practices, evaluate inequities that exist for a specific student or group of students, and improve your own classroom instruction.

Conclusions

The results showed that the level of instructional competence the School Heads are not giving a heads-up on how to achieve academic excellence. This is indicative of a serious academic blunder if it remains uncorrected because the teachers will become blind followers. As required, School Heads must be on top of the situation to be able to properly lead the teachers and the learners in achieving their desired academic goals. On one hand, some School Heads are not using the result of the classroom observation when coaching the teachers. The need to use the results of COT is critically important because it will ensure the objectivity of the School Heads in giving a sound feedback. Since the actual documentation of the classroom observation documents the areas for improvement, the School Head would be able to pin point and identify the areas needing proper attention. In the area of formative assessments, some School Heads lacks the leadership in implementing formative assessments. When School Heads fail to show that formative assessments are necessary, some teachers might indeed think that it is not as important and they may become passive in fully implementing formative assessment.

When grouped according to aforementioned variables, the results showed that some School Heads lacks the proper setting of expectations in achieving academic goals; the results showed that COT tools and its findings are not properly utilized to objectively provide feedback to teachers; and the result showed that low academic performers are not properly identified and given ample academic support. Foremost, the need to provide a heads-up on what to achieve in terms of academic goals must be set to ensure that all efforts are geared towards that goal. Secondly, when the result of the actual classroom observation is not used to coach and discuss plans with teachers, the very purpose of identifying areas for improvement will be defeated. The manner in which coaching is conducted will become arbitrary since the basis for the discussion is not objective. This may lead to an unfair coaching session with teachers. Lastly, it would always be difficult to provide differentiated instructions or additional academic assistance to bottom performers if they are not properly identified. It is only in properly recognizing the problem that the solution can be formulated.

The level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads in the area of financial management showed the need for some School Heads to practice transparency; some School Heads were unwilling to immediately resolve school conflict and disputes; and some school heads lack the initiative to help teachers grow professionally. The need for school Heads to be transparent with budget allocations is critically important because often times, this is where credibility issues come in. It is important that school heads make some efforts to rectify this shortcoming to maintain a healthy relationship with all sectors in his academic community. School heads must also show consistent willingness to resolve every dispute and conflicts because will initiate a crack in the concerted effort to achieve higher academic goals. Lastly, School Heads have the obligation to help provide opportunities for teachers to professionally grow as teachers for learners to benefit from the same.

When grouped according to aforementioned variables, the result showed that some School Heads are less transparent in allocating school budget; also, some School Heads lack the willingness to resolve conflicts within the

school; and there is a need for some School Heads to take the lead in providing various opportunities for teachers to improve their professional competence. Transparency in every financial dealing is important, therefore, School Heads must practice transparency to ensure that their credibility is maintained. School Heads unwillingness to resolve conflicts in school must be out of two reasons, lack of time to face conflicting parties or, his neutrality is compromised. Either of the two scenarios, internal school conflicts must be provided proper attention and resolution. Also, the opportunities for School Heads to assist their teachers to grow professionally is just around the corner, all the is needed to be done is for the School Heads to tap all other stakeholders to actively participate in improving teachers' professional competence.

The level of teachers' performance was very satisfactory. This clearly shows that there is still a large room for teachers to achieve outstanding performance in the course of their teaching years. By identifying the KPI's needing improvement, teachers will be able to pull up their performance properly.

There was no significant difference in the level of instructional competence of public elementary School Heads when they are grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables. It can be concluded that the opinion of the respondents in assessing the abilities of the School Heads instructional competence is at a high level. It can be equally concluded that teachers have higher regards for their School Heads instructional competence and leadership.

There was a significant difference in the level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads when they are grouped and compared according sex and highest educational attainment. Based on the result, it can be concluded that Male and female respondents have differing opinion in assessing School Heads, supervisory skills, the same is true with the respondents' highest educational attainment. The Male group has a different idea on how to lead or act as leaders, so does the female group. With regards to their highest educational attainment, those who have reached a higher degree of education may have a wider perspective as opposed to the other group.

There was no significant difference in the level of Teachers performance. It can be concluded that teachers are all keeping themselves within the ranks, otherwise, some may have fallen short of the very satisfactory level where they currently are.

There was no significant relationship between the level of instructional competence of public elementary School Heads and the level of teachers' performance. This goes to show that regardless of their school heads ability to lead or govern the school, teachers are going to perform the best they can to ensure that learners are given quality education. It can also be concluded based on the results that most teachers are independent-minded.

There was no significant relationship between the level supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads and the level of teachers' performance. This equally reveals that regardless of how skillful or how competent their School Heads, teachers are going to perform their tasks as educators. This means that, hyperbolically speaking, even if the teachers are assigned to a less skillful School Head, they will continue to perform as required of them.

Recommendations

Instructional Competence

Instructional Delivery. The results showed that instructional competence was high except for some issues identified like the setting of proper expectations. Without a doubt, School Heads are considered as seasoned educators. Come high or low, their instructional competence in delivering lesson content contents are at an all-time high. However, as School Heads, they must be able to able to set forth proper direction as to which way would he/she like the team to go in advancing towards academic excellence. It is recommended by this study that Proper Setting of Expectation be done each year during teachers' Orientation with School Level. All Plans must be laid down and stakeholders must also be involved. This way, everybody in the team will be aligned in working towards reaching the School's academic goals. Furthermore, it is recommended that there should be an acknowledgement form for all teachers to sign and acknowledge that the School Head was able to provide proper heads up on how to work as a team to achieve higher school objectives.

Classroom Observation. The result showed that at times, COT results are not being used in the course of the feedbacking with teachers. It is recommended that the School will have a structured coaching log for the School Heads and Teachers to sign. This coaching log with teachers will provide a better picture of each teachers' strength and weakness inside the classroom. This way, everything will be documented and the tendency to have an arbitrary discussion will be avoided. The School Head must discuss the Classroom Observation results with the teacher thoroughly and both must be able to acknowledge of the things discussed because it will be entered and logged.

Formative Assessment. The result showed that there is a need to identify low or bottom academic performers. This must fall within the responsibilities of the teachers, as it has always been. However, there is always a need to push the teachers into doing or implementing something to make them move due to the present workload of teachers. It is recommended by this study to have a localized School Memorandum from the School Heads regarding the identification of low/bottom performers and that they should be given proper attention. To ensure compliance, teachers must be able to acknowledge the memo.

Supervisory Skills

Financial Management. Some School Heads are not practicing transparency in allocating funds. This study would like to recommend that the School's Annual Financial Plan be posted in conspicuous places in school,

preferably, outside of the Principal's office. The same must be done for actual spending. This will help clarify issues and this, too, will encourage stake holders to partake in key school projects.

Conflict Management. School Heads at times are not willing to sit down with sparring parties. There is a need to resolve internal and smaller disputes. To avoid having doubts as to biases or personal reasons, School Heads may create a well-represented School Grievance Committee/Child Protection Policy Committee to help resolve conflicts and disputes within the School. It may be composed of PTA officers, Guidance Counselors, Master Teachers and other Senior Grade level teachers. This will ensure the balance composition of mediators within the school council.

Teachers' Professional Development. The result showed that some School Heads lacked the needed leadership in looking for support to help teachers' training or any other professional development courses. Most likely, it is the financial side of the said uptraining or Insets that needs support. It is recommended that School Heads will discuss possible financial support for upcoming trainings, seminars and workshops. This can be done through a well-represented committee who will assist the School Heads in scouting for support to ensure that teachers' training are well-supported and funded.

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